

Conductance Behaviour of some associated Hydrochlorides of Medicinal Interest in Aqueous Solution at 298 K

S. C. DUTTA, S. DAS** and S. C. LAHIRI*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235

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The conductance studies of hydrochlorides of well-known drugs (like pseudoephedrine, isoxsuprine, metoclopramide, pentazocine, propranolol, dicyclomine and DL-phenylpropanolamine) in aqueous solutions have been made. The analysis of the results using Shedlovsky's equation indicates that the compounds are associated in aqueous solutions. Improved values of the association constants K_A and Λ_0 have been determined using Fuoss equation. The Λ_0 values of the cations compare very well with those for tetraalkylammonium ions and it is expected that they undergo hydrophobic interactions in aqueous solutions.

WHATEVER effects a drug produces in a biologic system must be regarded as ultimate consequences of physicochemical interactions between that drug and functional important molecules in the living organism¹. Therefore, drug actions are physicochemical interactions of drug with the receptor (a macromolecule, where a drug interacts) to produce the characteristic biologic effect.

It is apparent that the pharmacological action of the drugs are to some extent dependent on their physicochemical properties^{2,3}. It is, therefore, desirable to make a systematic study of the various physicochemical properties of the medicinal compounds so that useful correlation can be made between the pharmacological action and the physicochemical properties of the drugs. Though some of the physicochemical properties have been studied in detail, the studies are in no way complete. The considerations led us to undertake such study.

Most of the reactions that are of biological and medicinal interest occur in solutions, the predominant solvent being water. The ion-solvent or solute-solvent interactions may be of great importance as very little amount of drug (often as low as $10^{-9}M$)⁴ is capable of bringing about an enormous change in the physiological system. Increase in concentrations of the drug sometimes reverses the effect⁴. Though the importance of ionic hydration in biophysics and biochemistry is known, relatively little work has been done on the ion-solvent (solute-solvent) interactions of the drugs. Therefore, concentrated effort should be made to know the ion-solvent interactions of the drug molecules.

Due to solubility limitations, most of the common drugs are used as hydrochlorides and due to the presence of amphipathic as well as amphiphilic groups in the same molecule, they form

micelles in solution. The studies of the physicochemical properties of the drugs, therefore, should give some valuable information regarding the mechanism of drug action. Studies on the transport properties like viscosity, conductivity and compressibility give useful informations regarding ion-solvent interactions. It is expected that the conductivity measurements of the drugs will provide useful information regarding structural interactions and their implications. These considerations led us to report the conductance studies of some of these drugs (as hydrochlorides) in an earlier paper⁵. The drugs were found to be unassociated in water.

We report in this communication the conductance behaviour of some associated hydrochlorides.

**Department of Chemistry, North Bengal University, Darjeeling-734 430.

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Experimental

The following medicinal compounds used for the study were purified by recrystallisation from the respective solvents (given in parenthesis): pseudoephedrine hydrochloride (1) (ethanol), isoxsuprine hydrochloride (2) (water), propranolol hydrochloride (3) (n-propanol), metoclopramide hydrochloride (4) (ethanol+water), pentazocine hydrochloride (5) (ethanol+water), DL-phenylpropranolamine hydrochloride (6) (ethanol+water) and dicyclomine hydrochloride (7) (butanone). The purity of the compounds ranged from 99.4 to 99.8%. Their solutions were made in conductivity (triple-distilled) water.

Conductance measurements of the drugs at different concentrations were done with a Leeds Northrup 4959 conductance bridge with a sensitivity of $\pm 0.1\%$; a 50 cycle signal was employed. A fairly long vertical dip type Philips conductance cell was fitted into a double-walled corning vessel containing the experimental solution. The temperature of the solution was maintained at 298 ± 0.01 K by passing thermostatic water (controlled by an accurate relay system) through the double-walled vessel. The system eliminated possible side-effects^{9,7}. The cell constant (0.76 cm^{-1}) was determined as suggested by Jones and Bradshaw⁸.

Results and Discussion

The conductance data were analysed using Shedlovsky's method⁹⁻¹¹ involving the sets of

equations (1-3),

$$\frac{1}{S\Lambda} = \frac{1}{\Lambda_0} + \frac{C\Delta S f_{\pm}^2 K_A}{\Lambda_0^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\log f_{\pm} = -\frac{1.8246 \times 10^6 (C\alpha)^{1/2} / (\epsilon T)^{3/2}}{1 + 50.29 \times 10^6 R(C\alpha)^{1/2} / (\epsilon T)^{1/2}} \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{S\Delta}{\Lambda_0} \quad (3)$$

As suggested by Justice¹², the Bjerrum critical distance, $q = e^2/2\epsilon kT$ has been put equal to R in equation (2). The terms in the equations have their usual significance. The initial values of Λ_0 have been obtained from the plot of Λ against $C^{1/2}$. The association constants (K_A) and the limiting equivalent conductances (Λ_0) have been iteratively calculated by a least-square treatment fitted to equations (1-3) using a BASIC programme; an Wipro Z-650 computer was used for the purpose. The Λ_0 and K_A values thus obtained are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCES AT 298 K USING FROSS (1978) EQUATION

Conc. (C) equiv. dm ⁻³	Λ (expt)	$\beta = 7.160 \text{ \AA}$				
		Λ_0	K_A	σ %	λ_{\pm}°	r_{\pm}°
Pseudoephedrine hydrochloride						
0.010	95.89					
0.004	100.70					
0.003	101.97	109.68	9.92	1.17	33.34	2.76
0.002	103.92					
0.001	107.75	109.40 ^a	8.57 ^a			
Isoxsuprine hydrochloride						
0.010	85.90					
0.005	91.02					
0.004	92.30	100.56	11.70	0.154	24.22	3.80
0.002	94.90	100.51 ^a	11.02 ^a			
0.001	97.00					
Metoclopramide hydrochloride						
0.010	78.67					
0.008	80.57					
0.006	83.76					
0.004	86.83	97.38	21.52	0.308	21.04	4.97
0.003	88.17	97.29 ^a	20.62 ^a			
0.002	90.33					
0.001	93.32					
Pentazocine hydrochloride						
0.010	74.53					
0.008	76.32					
0.006	78.76	92.78	22.75	0.344	18.44	4.99
0.004	81.73	93.30 ^a	23.13 ^a			
0.003	84.05					
0.002	86.21					
Propranolol hydrochloride						
0.010	80.30					
0.008	82.50					
0.006	85.70	102.17	27.83	0.322	25.83	3.56
0.004	89.00	101.91 ^a	26.43 ^a			
0.003	91.96					
0.002	94.25					

(Table 1 contd.)

Dicyclomine hydrochloride						
0.008	75.80					
0.006	77.95					
0.005	79.74	91.36	21.97	0.231	15.02	6.09
0.004	80.92	91.23 ^a	20.34 ^a			
0.002	84.90					
DL-Phenyl propanolamine hydrochloride						
0.01	86.90					
0.008	86.79					
0.006	89.44	107.52	28.06	0.667	31.18	2.94
0.005	92.32	106.69 ^a	25.73 ^a			
0.004	94.75					

*Ref. 13. ^aShedlovsky values.

Since K_A values have been found to be considerably greater than 10, the drugs can be regarded to be associated in water. The accurate results for these drugs can not be obtained using Fuoss-Onsager equation and the modified equation is to be used.

We have adopted the recent method of computation proposed by Fuoss¹³. For a set of conductance data (C_j , Δ_j , $J=1 \cdot n$), three adjustable parameters Δ_0 , K_A and R (co-sphere diameter) can be obtained by solving the equations,

$$\Delta = \gamma[\Delta_0(1 + RX) + EL] \quad (4)$$

$$\gamma = 1 - K_A C_j^2 f^2 \quad (5)$$

$$-\ln f = \beta/2(1 + KR) \quad (6)$$

$$\beta = \frac{e^2}{\epsilon KT} \quad (7)$$

RX and EL are relaxation and hydrodynamic terms, respectively. Expressions for RX and EL were the same as derived by Fuoss. The computation was done using a Fortran IV programme (kindly supplied by Professor Fuoss). The coarse scan for all salts from $R=2$ to $R=15$ with increments of 1 gave no significant minimum so the computations were done by fixing R at $\beta/2$.

The K_A , Δ_0 , β and $\sigma\% = 100\sigma/\Delta_0$ are given in Table 1,

where

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\sum_j (\Delta_j(\text{cal}) - \Delta_j(\text{obs}))^2}{n-2} \quad (8)$$

The recent Fuoss equation¹³ requires data of high precision (better than 0.05%). However, we do not claim such precision.

The limiting conductance values (Δ_0) and association constants (K_A) of the compounds (as hydrochlorides) obtained using Fuoss equation¹³ are recorded in Table 1. The Δ_0 values obtained using Shedlovsky's equation are also recorded for comparison. However, in absence of suitable data, it is not possible to compare the results.

The equivalent conductance of drugs at infinite dilutions are important as they effectively represent an interaction of drug cations with solvents (i.e. ion-solvent interactions). The effect of counterions like Cl^- is not of great consequence as it forms an essential constituent of physiological system.

The single ion conductance values (λ_i^0) represent the solvation of ions and capability of ions for diffusion towards the receptor site. It is well-known that most of these drugs are amphipathic in nature and usually form micelles. But at infinite dilution micellar properties are not important and micellar concentrations are rarely attained *in vivo* and therefore ion-solvent interactions may be of importance.

The Δ_0 values of the drug hydrochlorides at 298 K, vary from 90–110 since the value of $\lambda^0 \text{Cl}^-$ (76.34 or 76.39 at 298 K) in water is accurately known, λ_i^0 of drug cations can be calculated accurately. The λ_i^0 values of drug cations are recorded in Table 1. In general, these values at 298 K are close to $\lambda_{\text{Et}_4\text{N}^+}^0$, some of the values are close to $\lambda_{\text{Et}_4\text{N}^+}^0$ (32.22), which is neither a structure-breaker nor a structure-maker, but mostly closer to $\lambda_{\text{Pr}_4\text{N}^+}^0$ (23.22) and $\lambda_{\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+}^0$ (19.31), which are well-known structure-makers in water. However, all the drug cations are expected to undergo hydrophobic hydration. The extent of interactions can be guessed from the radii values of ions, which has been calculated from the conventional primitive model⁶ using equation (9),

$$R_i = \frac{0.819 Z}{\eta_0 \lambda_i} \quad (9)$$

where $\eta_0 = 8.03 \times 10^{-8} P$. The radii values are also listed in Table 1. The radii of the cations of these drugs are not known but the approximate calculation of the radius of phenothiazine moiety comes out to be 3.3–3.4 Å.

In general, the radii of the ions determined using equation (9) do not represent the Stokes' radii of ions. Our value for $r_{\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+} = 4.66$ Å compares well with the value 4.71 given by Robinson and Stokes¹⁷. (The $r_{\text{BPh}_4^-}$ and $r_{\text{AsPh}_4^+}$ values determined by us are 4.95 and 5.26 Å respectively). The Stokes' radii (r_s) calculated from the limiting conductivity values have been found to be less than the true hydrated radii of ions¹⁷. Robinson and Stokes¹⁷ observed low values of r for tetraalkyl ammonium ions from conductance values and applied suitable corrections to obtain the true dimensions of tetraalkylammonium ions.

We have not used correction to get the radii of hydrated ions and in absence of the true values of the radii of ions, the hydration number can not be determined. It is to be noted that the ions are not symmetrical in nature and in case of these large and unsymmetrical molecules, it is extremely difficult to estimate the radii from the bond lengths or models as too many configurations exist. It is reasonable to assume that hydrophobic interactions of drug molecules with water play an important role in determining the activities of the drug molecules.

The drugs under study are different chemically, structurally and pharmacologically and obviously the nature of hydration and the radii of the hydrated cations would be considerably different but the

radii values would be greater or nearly equal to the pore size (4 Å) of the lipoprotein membranes.

The cations can be assumed to be strongly bound by the water molecules leading to an increase in the radii of the ions and it is rational to think that the drugs do not pass through the pores of the semipermeable membrane of the cells as ions but they are converted to neutral molecule and go into lipophilic layers by partition technique to exert their biologic activity. However, in case of associated salts, the drugs may partially pass through the cell membrane as such.

However, it is necessary to undertake systematic studies to say something positively on the transport properties of the drug molecules.

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